

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of 1-Aryl/alkyl/aralkyl Dithiourazoles

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Thiele and Strange¹ found hydrazodicarbonamide to readily split out ammonia to form urazole. The sulphur analogue may split out either hydrogen sulphide or ammonia². Recently Dubenko and Pelkis³ have prepared several monoaryl dithiohydrazodicarbonamides and cyclised them to 1-aryldithiourazoles.

It was of interest to us to study 1,6-di-substituted dithiohydrazodicarbonamides for their cyclisation in order to evaluate the orientation and stability of different alkyl, aralkyl, and aryl substituents.

It is observed in the present study that during cyclisation of 1-aryl-6-alkyl- and 1,6-diaryl-dithiohydrazodicarbonamides, the lighter aryl group (phenyl in the present investigation) is preferentially eliminated. The constitution of the final dithiourazoles has been confirmed by cyclisation of symmetrically 1,6-di-substituted dithiohydrazodicarbonamides and by their mixed melting points with the products obtained by cyclisation of unsymmetrical 1,6-di-substituted products.

Table I describes various dithiohydrazodicarbonamides and Table II describes their cyclisation products. Table III records the symmetrical 1,6-disubstituted dithiohydrazodicarbonamides, prepared for cyclisation to confirm the constitution of dithiourazoles obtained in the previous method. The melting points recorded in the tables are uncorrected.

Various isothiocyanates were prepared from the corresponding amines by a standard procedure of Moore and Crossley⁴. 4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide was prepared by the interaction of phenyl isothiocyanate and hydrazine hydrate according to Pulvermacher⁵. A typical procedure for the synthesis of 1,6-di-substituted dithiohydrazodicarbonamide is described below.

Synthesis of 1-Phenyl-6-p-bromophenyldithiohydrazodicarbonamide.—Equimolar quantities of 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide and phenyl isothiocyanate were refluxed in excess of ethanol for about 2 hr. Partial evaporation of ethanol left a product which was repeatedly crystallised from dilute ethanol until an analytically pure sample was obtained. The product melted at 130°.

In majority of cases one recrystallisation was found satisfactory.

1. *Annalen*, 1894, 283, 6.
2. *Freund, Ber.*, 1893, 26, 2977; 1896, 23, 946; 1896, 23, 2500.
3. *Z. Obst. Klim.*, 1962, 32, 939; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, 58, 3447.
4. *Org. Syn.*, Vol. 21, p. 81.
5. *Ber.*, 1899, 26, 281; 1894, 27, 622.

The average yields of products, thus prepared and described in Table I, are in the range of 60 to 65%.

TABLE I
1-Phenyl-6-substituted aryl/alkyl/aralkyl-hydrazodithiocarbonamides.

$$\text{Ph-NH-C(=S)-NH-NH-C(=S)-NH-R}$$

No.	R.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	Ph	190°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂	20.0	21.2
2	<i>p</i> -Tol	187°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂	20.3	20.2
3	<i>m</i> - "	173°	"	20.2	20.2
4	<i>o</i> - "	180°	"	20.3	20.2
5	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	205°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₄ ClS ₂	18.8	19.1
6	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	130°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₄ BrS ₂	16.5	16.8
7	<i>p</i> -IC ₆ H ₄	105°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₄ IS ₂	15.0	15.0
8	<i>p</i> -OMe.C ₆ H ₄	190°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S ₂	19.3	19.6
9	<i>o</i> - "	120°	"	19.4	19.6
10	2,5(CH ₃ O) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	140°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂	17.6	17.7
11	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	175°	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂	20.1	20.3
12	C ₆ H ₁₁ (cyclohexyl)	200°	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ S ₂	20.8	20.7
13	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	150°	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂	22.6	22.7
14	<i>n</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁	175°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂	21.8	21.6
15	<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃	176°	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂	20.7	20.7

TABLE II
1-Aryl/alkyl/aralkyl-dithiourazoles.

*No.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.
1	110°	C ₆ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂	30.3	30.6
2	230°	C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	28.5	28.7
3	95°	"	28.4	28.7
4	80°	"	28.5	28.7
5	115°	C ₆ H ₆ N ₃ ClS ₂	28.1	28.3
6	78°	C ₆ H ₆ N ₃ BrS ₂	22.2	22.5
7	125°	C ₆ H ₆ N ₃ IS ₂	19.0	19.1
8	205°	C ₇ H ₇ ON ₃ S ₂	27.0	26.8
9	183°	"	26.9	26.8
10	83°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	23.5	23.8
11	215°	C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	28.5	28.7
12	163°	C ₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	29.6	29.8
13	95°	C ₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	34.0	33.9
14	117°	C ₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	31.7	31.5
15	125°	C ₈ H ₁₅ K ₃ S ₂	29.3	29.5

*R is same as in Table I.

1-*p*-Bromophenyldithiourazole. — 1-Phenyl-6-*p*-bromophenyldithiohydrazodicarbonamide (1 g.) was taken in 2*N*-NaOH solution (10 ml) and refluxed on a sand bath for 2 hr: On cooling and acidifying with HCl(dil.), the precipitated product was collected at the pump and crystallised from ethanol, yield 0.4g. One recrystallisation from ethanol afforded a pure product. The average yield of various dithiourazoles, prepared by above method and described in Table III, was about 48 to 55%.

TABLE III

1,6-Symmetrically di-substituted hydrazodithiocarbonamides.

No.	R.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	<i>p</i> -Tol	215°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ S ₂	19.2	19.4
2	<i>o</i> - "	185°	"	19.3	19.4
3	<i>m</i> - "	190°	"	19.2	19.4
4	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	195°	C ₁₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂	24.2	24.4
5	<i>n</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁	190°	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ N ₄ S ₂	22.0	22.1
6	<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃	186°	C ₁₄ H ₃₀ N ₄ S ₂	20.0	20.1

Table III describes various symmetrical di-substituted hydrazodithiocarbonamides. Cyclisation of these products yielded compounds No. 2, 4, 3, 13, 14, and 15, respectively (vide Table II).

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Received December 24, 1964.